

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Version 1 of reduced precision tools are available for
download and use
Milestone M2.1**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.1

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.1

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

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See the original description in the [Grant Agreement](#)

Dissemination level:

See the original description in the [Grant Agreement](#)

Delivery date:

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Means of verifications:

Tools published and available online

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

Does not apply

Comments:

Nothing else to comment.

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Status: December 20th, 2024

AutoRPE is a tool designed to help with the **optimization of the numerical precision** of Computational Science models written in Fortran. As part of this milestone, the AutoRPE repository has been made publicly accessible at earth.bsc.es/gitlab/ces/hpc-for-es-team/AutoRPE, ensuring transparency and fostering collaboration. Additionally, a Zenodo entry has been created for the source code of release 1.0, enabling proper citation and long-term preservation (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14535414>). To facilitate easy installation, AutoRPE has been published on PyPI, allowing users to install it quickly using pip. Finally, documentation is now available at <https://autorpe.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.